

COVID^X

How to Understand the Sandbox Without Having Technical knowledge

Within COVID-X, three technical partners helped the Game Changers understand the Sandbox, and how it works to ingest and deal with their data...But, what exactly is the Sandbox?

[Learn more about the Sandbox](#)

COVID X vs Healthcare Policy

COVID-X Anonymisation Guide: Data Anonymisation through the lenses of Clinical Ambassador SERMAS.

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